

THE EMERGENCE OF THE GERMAN LEGAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: It is known that the history of German jurisprudence from a legal-historical point of view includes legal knowledge based on tribal rights and, in particular, Saxon and Frankish legal concepts. Together with Roman and canon law, it formed the common jurisprudence of the High Middle Ages and formed a trio of legal sources that were decisive in the development of European jurisprudence.

Keywords: German-canonical Roman, Germanic jurisprudence, Middle Ages, Saxon Mirror.

Introduction

In this sense, German jurisprudence should not be confused with actual jurisprudence in Germany. It refers only to the historical period and its legal traditions, and we can observe that German jurisprudence began in the 6th century of the Middle Ages and continued until the beginning of the 12th century. Accordingly, modern studies assume that a single whole German system was formed in the Middle Ages. To this day, German-canonical Roman legal traditions coexist in Germany, and the current legal system relies on all of these sources.

It is known from German historical times that ancient Germanic law was accepted orally.

Pre-medieval Germanic jurisprudence expressed the rights of the people's courts orally. Tribal rights and Germanic national rights were created for members of individual tribes during the migration of peoples [1. 35].

The Main Findings and Results

In the Middle Ages, tribal rights, originating from early medieval hierarchical societies, arose as land rights for the inhabitants of a specific geographical area. In addition, there were special rights for certain professional groups or groups of people. Ownership of land and property and related services and obligations began to express the main direction of the legal system. The legal system of the nobility consisted essentially of feudal law. Peasants were partly free and legally

independent landowners, partly joined to the church. Reich legislation was limited to separate constitutional laws. For example, the Golden Bull of 1356. It can be concluded that 13th century law books such as Mühlhausen's Reich Law, Sachsenspiegel (Saxon Mirror) or Schwabenspiegel (Swabian Mirror) contributed greatly to legal harmonization. In particular, the Sachsenspiegel (Saxon Mirror) has survived largely unscathed from the later Middle Ages and early modern period [1. 47]. During our research, we observed that German legislation was strong in the Middle Ages.

We will dwell on the legal relations of feudalism in the social system in Germany, an agrarian country characterized by a natural economy. The upper class, the land-owning nobles divided into different property groups, and the lower class, the peasants who worked the land, began to develop [2. 69]. Only at the beginning of the High Middle Ages, that is, in the second half of the 12th century, we can observe the development of trade and monetary relations with cities, and with it the regulatory aspects of mutual relations was not yet available. The order of estates created in the Middle Ages was preserved until the French Revolution. The social order was characterized by a limited bourgeoisie and the exclusion of the nobility from political decision-making at the same time [2. 70]. It should be noted that in the High Middle Ages, unlike today, the judges were only responsible for negotiating with the judges and announcing the verdict with the judges.

The judge himself did not have the right to make a decision. The main actions of the party created strong binding effects, which led to the emergence of the habit of entrusting them to lawyers for their existence. Evidence was an oath (often administered by oath-takers) and a judicial duel, which decided guilt and innocence as a divine judgment. Sentences did not depend on legal remedies in the modern sense, as a result of which we can observe that there was an immediate trial between the prosecutor and the judge. Punishments in Germanic times were physical injuries from the early Middle Ages. In the Middle Ages, there was a general trend of infamous interrogations, mirror punishments under the law, and capital punishment under torture.

Between the 13th and 16th centuries, a legal profession emerged that taught and studied Latin. It has been taught in written Roman law and canon law created by the Catholic Church. The emergence of learned jurists in German legal practice began the adoption of Roman law, as medieval culture was influenced by the Latin language. A number of official and private works of Emperor Frederick III are recorded in writing. In connection with the reform of the constitutional

structures, it is also known that in the 1440s the doctors of jurisprudence had a large voice in the council meetings and in the courts [3. 98].

Starting from the second half of the 15th century, Roman law, the modern law taught in Italy, influenced the law. Although the law existed only as an adjunct to local and regional laws, they were often romanized, i.e. adapted to Roman law. The transition from oral to clandestine proceedings created a estrangement between people and people.

With the Enlightenment period, a decisive turn in the legal system took place, a new social theory was developed that adopted the form of the medieval society. From the 18th century, we can observe that the German law grew stronger.

As a result of historical development, Roman law began to have a significant influence on the development of the German legal system. Although the Germanic tribes had their own legal traditions, which were written down in their code of laws after the fall of the Western Roman Empire, these tribes settled in former Rome and therefore had to incorporate the more familiar Roman law into their legal traditions. It's done. During our research we learned that there were times when there was no written law in the early Middle Ages [3. 101].

It was different only in the ecclesiastical area, where since the beginning of the Middle Ages written church law was also subordinated to church law. In addition to members of the clergy, the poor, widows, orphans, and crusaders were subject to the existing law. From the twelfth century, it is noted that local customs are not thematically sorted as the best. Examples of this are the Saxon Window and the Swabian Window, which show typical events of the Germanic legal tradition, such as the payment of fines to the relatives of a criminal.

The Roman foundation of the *corpus iuris civilis*, written by the Eastern Roman Emperor Justinian (527-565), spread throughout Europe through the Italian law schools. Roman law was used mainly when no solution was offered. Rational law became widespread during the Enlightenment period. Roman is interpreted and adapted in a modern way [3. 114].

Conclusion

In Germany, small nation-states were formed, in which in 1794 the General Prussian State Law (ALR), i.e., a law based on the traditional privileges of the nobility, was created, which included all existing rights.

After a long preliminary search, the Citizenship Act was promulgated in 1896, which came into force on January 1, 1900.

The main feature of German legislation during the Second World War was to prevent an unjust regime like the National Socialist era in the future. Each law had to be measured against the standards of the 1949 German Basic Law [9]. In conclusion, it can be said that the emergence or development of the legal system of each country goes through certain historical periods.

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